

INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION CAPABILITIES ON SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE AMONG SMES IN KWARA STATE

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Abstract

In resource- and infrastructure-constrained developing economies, digital transformation has emerged as a key driver of SME competitiveness advantage. This paper examines the influence of digital transformation capabilities on sustainable competitive advantage for SMEs in Kwara State, Nigeria, drawing on diffusion of innovation theory and the resource-based view. In particular, the paper explores how digital infrastructure capabilities affect customer loyalty and retention, and the role of digital capabilities in sustainable, innovative performance. A cross-sectional survey design was used, and 360 SME owners and managers were surveyed using a structured questionnaire. The study hypotheses were tested using descriptive statistics and inferential analysis. The results indicate that the impact of digital infrastructure capability on customer loyalty and customer retention is positive and statistically significant, but of low intensity, suggesting that digital infrastructure could be perceived as an enabling environment for customer outcomes. On the contrary, digital skills have a strong and significant effect on sustainable innovation performance, explaining a high percentage of the variation in innovation sustainability in SMEs. The discoveries were used to emphasise that digital infrastructure is required, but the critical factor in determining the extent to which digital resources are converted into long-term competitive advantage and sustained innovation is the development of digital skills among owners and employees. However, the owners and managers of SMEs are advised to be more strategic in their digital transformation practices by moving beyond the acquisition of basic digital infrastructure to the systematic development of digital capabilities within their firms.

Keywords: Digital transformation, digital capabilities, sustainability, competitive advantage.

JEL Code: O31; O32; L26.

1. Introduction

The concept of digital transformation has been widely discussed and emerged as a principle of competitiveness in the modern business environment, and the role of

digital capabilities in improving firm performance has been highlighted in the previous literature. (Salimi & Chandrasekar, 2025; Subramaniam & Teh, 2026) Meanwhile, the accessible literature, predominantly based on the resource-based and the dynamic capabilities perspectives, indicates that firms that successfully deploy and reorganise digital assets are in a better place to address market turmoil and keep ahead of competitors. (Kumar & Sharma, 2025) The purpose of digital transformation capabilities (DTCs) is to provide strategic resources for SMEs to alleviate structural issues associated with poor capital, market accessibility, and organisational inefficiencies. (Idzni et al., 2025) Despite observations from developed economies, studies on the Nigerian environment are predominantly adoption-based and technologically deterministic (Afolabi et al., 2021; Solomon et al., 2024); little attention is given to digital transformation as a multidimensional, capability-based process. Most of the studies provide a focus on the question of the usage of digital technologies, i.e. mobile banking, social media, or e-commerce systems by SMEs, and do not discuss the capabilities of an organisation to incorporate these tools into its strategic and operational practices. (Chukwunweike & Gift, 2025; Dakare & Okon, 2024)

Moreover, competitive advantage is commonly evaluated on short-term performance, ignoring whether digital transformation can help SMEs develop a sustainable competitive advantage in an environment defined by infrastructural deficits and volatile markets. Empirical data is especially meagre at the subnational level. For example, in Kwara State, where SMEs are the predominant source of employment and local economic growth, there is an evident lack of studies analysing the impact of firm-level digital transformation skills on long-run competitiveness. As a result, there is very limited knowledge on the channels through which SMEs in Kwara State transform digital efforts into sustainable strategic advantages.

This research gap has immense theoretical and empirical implications. In theory, the narrow scope of research on digital transformation skills limits the applicability of traditional strategic management theories to the Nigerian SME context, where institutional and infrastructural environments differ significantly from those in developed economies. (Felzensztein et al., 2022; Youssef et al., 2023) In practice, Kwara State SMEs are forced to work within resource constraints, an unpredictable power supply, poor network connections, inadequate digital skills, and limited social networks. (Ibrahim et al., 2025; Olawale & Balogun, 2025) In the absence of sufficient evidence on which DTCs are relevant to sustainable competitive advantage, owners of SMEs may be tempted to make a costly bet on digital transformation, which yields only short-term benefits. (Mustapha et al., 2025) To fill this gap, a study of how DTCs affect the sustainable competitive advantage of SMEs in Kwara state, Nigeria, is required. Hence, research questions are formed:

- i. What is the effect of digital infrastructure capability on customer loyalty and

retention among SMEs in Kwara State

- ii. How does digital skills capability influence sustainable innovative performance among SMEs in Kwara State

2. Literature Review

Digital Transformation Capabilities

The literature shows that Digital Transformation Capabilities (DTC) are an organisation's proficiencies for successfully deploying and integrating digital technologies to change business processes, create value, and respond to dynamic environments. (Kumar & Sharma, 2025; Pakdel et al., 2025) It presupposes a focus not only on the use of digital technologies but also on the organisational ability to successfully utilise these tools to create a long-term competitive advantage. (Bin-Salleh et al., 2025) However, in line with this perspective, DTC are operationalised in two dimensions, Digital Infrastructure Capability (DIC) and Digital Skills Capability (DSC). (Bin-Salleh et al., 2025) DIC can be defined as the presence and successful utilisation of underlying digital technologies that provide connectivity, information processing and digital interaction. (Battistoni et al., 2023) Aside from that, it provides the technological framework on which digital transformation initiatives are anchored, which are usually manifested on two sub-dimensions, namely: (a) access to the internet and digital devices and (b) use of digital platforms. (Kumar & Sharma, 2025) Meanwhile, DSC is the human capital aspect of the digital transformation, encompassing the knowledge and skills needed to successfully utilise digital technologies within the firm. According to Ali-Alobaydi et al. (2025), digital transformation is essentially a socio-technical process, which involves technological resources and talented actors. This ability is mostly manifested in the digital literacy of the owner and employees. (Herasymchuk et al., 2025)

Sustainable Competitive Advantage (SCA)

SCA has a strong ability to maintain high performance over the long term compared to competitors by utilising resources and capabilities that are difficult to substitute, imitate, or duplicate (Subramaniam & Teh, 2026). In this research, customer retention and loyalty, and sustainable, innovative performance are chosen as the dimensions of the SCA (Subramaniam & Teh, 2026). Relational resources that are crucial for lowering the costs of acquiring and marketing products and services are less price-resistant and offer reliable streams of income, including customer loyalty and retention (Reimann et al., 2022). Thus, long-term customer retention helps a firm maintain its position and competitive advantage in the market. Sustainable, innovative performance is defined as the capacity to develop and implement innovations aligned with the firm's environmental and market dynamics (Reimann et al., 2022). Individual innovations are also prone to short-livedness in dynamic

markets; hence, organisations should adopt strategies to build sustained innovation (Subramaniam & Teh, 2026).

Theoretical Framings

Diffusion of Innovations (DOI) Theory

Rogers (2003) facilitates the DOI to describe the process of innovation spreading and being integrated over time within the members of a social system. It is a theory that the adoption process is determined by perceived innovation attributes, namely relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. Rogers, (2003; Whang et al., 2025) The theory has been largely adopted, especially when discussing the innovation of products and services. Despite widespread adoption, the theory was criticised for focusing on adoption decisions rather than capability development and performance outcomes. (Sima et al., 2025; Whang et al., 2025) Whang et al. (2025) argue that DOI is overly rationalistic and fails to adequately consider resource constraints and power asymmetries commonly encountered by SMEs. Besides, DOI offers little clarification on how adoption leads to sustained competitive advantage, and this requires incorporation with strategic management perspectives. However, the DOI can explain differences in the timing and pace of digital technology adoption. This implies that SMEs that see digital technologies as clear benefits and as strategically aligned are more likely to adopt new technologies and move towards advanced digital transformation. (Sima et al., 2025) The adoption and utilisation can be applied in the early stages to allow SMEs to establish digital transformation potentials, which facilitate innovation and competitive advantage

Resource-Based View (RBV)

Barney (1991) developed the RBV postulating that firms attain sustainable competitive advantage through the presence and utilisation of resources and capabilities that are valuable, rare, difficult to imitate, and non-substitutable (VRIN). Although the theory places less emphasis on external market conditions and internal firm strength as the main sources of long-term competitiveness. (Hu & Kee, 2022) Meanwhile, the purpose of the theory is to provide a theoretical framework for understanding digital transformation capabilities as a strategic asset. However, the RBV was criticised for being a static orientation, as it is not entirely based on the development of capabilities in rapidly changing digital environments. (Hu & Kee, 2022) Bin-Salleh et al. (2025) argue that RBV should be expanded by incorporating dynamic capability conceptions to elucidate continuous digital rejuvenation. In the case of SMEs, digital leadership, IT infrastructure integration, data analytics, and process reconfiguration are intangible capabilities that are not easily duplicated by rivals. This implies that such abilities will allow SMEs to perform at higher levels and gain a sustainable competitive advantage when well established and entrenched in organisational practices. (Kumar & Sharma, 2025; Yilin et al., 2022).

Hypotheses Development

Research Kumar and Sharma (2025) indicates that SMEs with digital infrastructures are more competitive with larger companies in terms of convenience and consistency, which positively affects customer repeat purchase behaviour and loyalty. Also, the existing literature connects loyalty and retention to perceived value, trust, and relationship quality, which are enhanced by efficient digital infrastructure. (Bin-Salleh et al., 2025; Subramaniam & Teh, 2026) Nevertheless, studies also report minimal effects in conditions of underutilisation of digital infrastructure or low customer digital literacy, suggesting that the effect may differ by location and firm capacity; hence, a hypothesis is formed:

H₀₁: Digital infrastructure capability has no significant effect on customer loyalty and retention among SMEs in Kwara State

Similarly, previous studies have shown that digital skills are an important prerequisite for innovation and sustainability, enabling SMEs to constantly adjust processes, products, and services to environmental changes. (Junaidi et al., 2025; Salimi & Chandrasekar, 2025) Salimi and Chandrasekar (2025) found that employees with digital skills are better positioned to discover market opportunities, adopt new technologies, and implement new solutions, thereby improving the firm's long-term performance. Unfortunately, many studies have allayed fears about the sustainability of this performance. (Bin-Salleh et al., 2025; Noer et al., 2025) However, the correlation can be weak or insignificant when SMEs lack complementary resources; hence, a hypothesis is formed:

H₀₂: Digital skills capability has no significant influence on sustainable innovative performance among SMEs in Kwara State

Conceptual Framework

Building on the empirical and theoretical framings of this study, Fig. 1 proposes that companies can gain a sustainable advantage by developing, deploying, and integrating digital resources into strategic and operational activities. Within this framework, the capability of digitally adept owners and staff to improve the firm's sense-making of market opportunities, adapt to the environment, and realign resources with the agents of change would lead to a heightened capacity to respond to environmental stimuli. The concept of sustainable competitive advantage is viewed in the context of customer retention and loyalty, as well as sustainable innovative performance. To improve generalizability, future research should expand the analysis to multiple regions or even countries, enabling comparative research across diverse institutional and technological conditions.

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework; Author (2026)

3. Methodology

This study employs a cross-sectional design, and the survey method is suitable for collecting information from a sample and extrapolating the results to the entire population. The method also allows researchers to assess the relationships among variables of interest. (Subramaniam & Teh, 2026) Aside from the choice of cross-sectional survey method, the method is based on its ability to collect data from multiple respondents simultaneously. (Rahmani et al., 2024) However, due to the nature of this study, which is premised on the digital transformation and capabilities, the population comprised all stakeholders of the SMEs' Payment Service Banks (PSBs) operators. This includes SMEs that operate formally or informally and directly use financial services (such as owners, managers, and micro-enterprise operators) within PSBs. Also, the agents operating under PSBs to deliver last-mile financial services, and PSB's customer service officers and POS/mobile money agents. In Kwara State, there are 717,909 registered SMEs and 78,198 PSB agents, according to information from SMEDAN (2020), NCC (2025b), and NBS (2025). (Mustapha et al., 2025; Olawale & Balogun, 2025)

However, the study employed Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) method via Raosoft online to determine the sample size. (Mustapha et al., 2025) Therefore, at a 5% margin of error, the distribution for 1 degree of freedom at a sample size of 383. This study employs a multi-stage sampling technique to select samples at multiple stages. (Ibrahim et al., 2025) The advantage of multi-stage sampling is that it enables a more efficient, cost-effective way to obtain a representative sample of the population (Saunders et al., 2018).

Instrumentation and Data Collection Methods

To ensure the instrument used in this study was both valid and reliable, a pilot study was conducted to develop valid measurement scales. First, item pools were

generated from an extensive literature review for each respective scale. Second, a series of validity and reliability tests was conducted to assess the scale's psychometric properties and ensure its adequacy for measuring the study variables. The items of digital infrastructure capability were derived from Mustapha et al. (2025); items from customer loyalty and retention were adopted from Ashiru et al. (2023). Also, items on digital skills capability were adopted from Ashiru et al. (2023), while items on sustainable innovative performance were adopted from Ludovico et al. (2025). However, to ensure that the research instrument used in this study was internally consistent and statistically reliable, Cronbach's Alpha (α) was tested, and all constructs are above 0.70. (Hong et al., 2021; Sukri et al., 2023)

In the process, three (3) Research Assistants (RAs) were recruited from Kwara Central, Kwara North and Kwara South for data collection. They were trained on the research's purpose and their roles throughout the exercise, which were to serve as guides in their respective areas. They assisted the researcher in following up and retrieving copies of the questionnaires from respondents. The questionnaire was designed in two (2) forms, 1. Google Form versions and 2. The hard-copy versions, which were primarily completed by staff of the SME owners, who were PSB agents. Descriptive statistics: frequency distributions and percentages were used to analyse the respondents' socio-demographic characteristics. Inferential statistics (regression analysis) were used to examine the relationships among the study variables.

4. Result and Discussion

Of the 383 targeted audience, only 360 Copies of the questionnaire were administered, completed, returned, and found usable for this analysis, yielding a response rate of about 94%.

Table 2: Respondents' Demographics

Constructs		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	237	65.8
	Female	123	34.2
Age	25-34 years	123	34.2
	35-44 years	123	34.2
	45-54 years	66	18.3
	55 years and above	48	13.3
Marital	Single	150	41.7
	Married	174	48.3
	Widow/Widower	24	6.7
	Divorced	12	3.3
Education	NCE/OND	36	10
	Bachelor's or equivalent	279	77.5
	Postgraduate	45	12.5

Length in the business	Less than 5 years	75	20.8
	5-10 years	117	32.5
	11-20 years	90	25.0
	20 years and above	75	20.8
Total		360	100.0

The information presented in Table 2 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. There are favourable conditions for the effective implementation of digital transformation among SMEs in Kwara State. For example, the educational level and economic activity of the respondents precondition a high level of ability to obtain knowledge digitally and to transform it into strategies that promote efficiency and responsiveness to market changes. Moreover, the presence of both older and younger firms suggests that digital transformation may serve not only to reaffirm current competitive advantage and presence but also to create sustainable competitive advantage in difficult, competitive markets.

Descriptive Analyses of the Constructs

Table 3: Respondents' Views on digital infrastructure capability on customer loyalty and retention among SMEs

Constructs	SD		D		N		A		SA	
	Frq	%								
	33	9.2	66	18.3	9	2.5	132	36.7	120	33.3
Reliable digital infrastructure helps our business maintain long-term customer relationships.	45	12.5	57	15.8	51	14.2	117	32.5	90	25.0
Our digital infrastructure allows us to respond quickly to customer needs	42	11.7	24	6.7	24	6.7	144	40.0	126	35.0
Digital tools and technologies used by our firm enhance customer satisfaction	48	13.3	12	3.3	6	1.7	159	44.2	135	37.5
Improvements in our digital infrastructure have led to higher customer retention	18	5.0	9	2.5	6	1.7	201	55.8	126	35.0

Table 3 presents the digital infrastructure capability and its impact on customer loyalty and retention among SMEs in Kwara State. In all the answers, agreement (A + SA) is consistently more relevant than disagreement (SD + D), indicating that the respondents view digital infrastructure as a basic component of customer-related

outcomes. The number of people who had reservations about the role of digital infrastructure in maintaining long-term relationships with customers is medium, but the positive (57.5) is still higher than the negative. These results therefore support the thesis that, in addition to operational benefits, investments in digital infrastructure will form strategic resources that directly create sustainable competitive advantage for SMEs.

Table 4: Respondents' Views on Digital Skills Capability Influence Sustainable Innovative Performance Among SMEs

Constructs	SD		D		N		A		SA	
	Frq	%								
	42	11.7	129	35.8	45	12.5	138	38.3	6	1.7
Employees' digital competencies help our firm adopt innovative processes	81	22.5	105	29.2	21	5.8	147	40.8	6	1.7
Digital skills within our firm support continuous improvement and long-term sustainability	6	1.7	0	0	0	0	234	65.0	120	33.3
The use of advanced digital tools and skills has increased the efficiency and sustainability	27	7.5	114	31.7	6	1.7	189	52.5	24	6.7
Our ability to use digital technologies enhances knowledge sharing	42	11.7	66	18.3	18	5.0	183	50.8	51	14.2

Table 4 shows that digital skills capability is an important determinant of sustainable innovative performance of SMEs in Kwara State. The vast majority of respondents confirmed that digital skills contribute to improvement and long-term sustainability, and most indicated agreement or strong agreement, suggesting that SMEs view digital capabilities as strategic rather than operational. Nevertheless, the rates of agreement on developing innovative products or services are lower than those, suggesting that, even though digital skills are actively employed to enhance processes and efficiency, the extent of their application to product and service development has not yet been fully utilised in some SMEs. These results suggest that digital transformation capabilities are crucial to developing sustainable competitive advantage among SMEs in Kwara State.

Test of Hypothesis

Table 5: Digital infrastructure capability and customer loyalty and retention among SMEs in Kwara State

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²		Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.176 ^a	.309	.0333		.53971	
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	3.15	1	3.150	6.013	.004 ^b
	Residual	101.362	167	.362		
	Total	104.512	168			
Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	T	Sig.	
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	2.123	.506		2.330	.000
	Digital infrastructure capability	.121	.033	.198	2.831	.004

a. Dependent Variable: customer loyalty and retention

b. Predictors: (Constant), Digital infrastructure capability

Table 5 presents a regression analysis of the association between digital infrastructure capability and customer loyalty and retention ($R = 0.176$). The coefficient of determination indicates that the digital infrastructure capability has moderate explanatory power for the model, accounting for about 31% of the variation in customer loyalty and retention ($R^2 = 0.309$). This suggests that the capability of digital infrastructure is relevant to creating customer loyalty and retention, but other variables not reflected in the model explain a greater % of the variation. The ANOVA in the table indicates that the regression equation is significant ($F(1, 167) = 6.013, p = 0.004$). This shows that digital infrastructure capability are crucial predictors of customer loyalty and retention among SMEs in Kwara State. The additional analysis of the regression coefficients reveals that digital infrastructure capability has a positive, statistically significant impact on customer loyalty and retention ($b = 0.198, t = 2.831, p = 0.004$). The unstandardised coefficient ($B = 0.121$) indicates that, other things held constant, a one-unit increase in digital infrastructure capability increases customer loyalty and retention by 0.121. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{0i}) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted that digital infrastructure capability has a significant effect on customer loyalty and retention among SMEs in Kwara State at the 5% sig. level.

Table 6: Digital skills capability and sustainable innovative performance among SMEs in Kwara State

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²		Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.641 ^a	.410	.420		.46533	
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	46.235	1	46.235	144.667	.000 ^b
	Residual	62.961	197	.320		
	Total	109.196	198			
Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-.543	.326		-1.296	.006
	Digital skills capability	.366	.010	.651	12.028	.000

a. Dependent Variable: sustainable innovative performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Digital skills capability

The regression analysis of the relationship between digital skills capability and sustainable and innovative performance among the SMEs in Kwara State is provided in Table 6. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.641$) indicates a strong positive association between the predictor and the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.410$) indicates that digital skills capability is a good, sustainable, and innovative performance that can be explained by about 41.0 per cent of the variance. The ANOVA results indicate that the regression model is significant ($F(1, 197) = 144.667, p < 0.001$). This indicates that predictive validity for sustainable and innovative performance is significantly higher when digital skills are included than in a model without any predictors. Additional evidence of the influence of digital skills capabilities is provided by the regression coefficients: Digital skills capability can significantly, positively, and statistically significantly affect sustainable, innovative performance ($b = 0.651, t = 12.028, p < 0.001$). The standardised ($b = 0.651$) is significant and demonstrates that digital skills are a determining factor in sustainable, innovative performance. The H_{02} is rejected because digital skills have a strong positive effect on sustainable innovation performance ($p < 0.05$). Digital skills are therefore a key success factor for sustainable and innovative performance amongst SMEs in Kwara State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings demonstrate that digital infrastructure capability has a positive, statistically significant impact on customer loyalty and customer retention among SMEs in Kwara State. Even though the relationship is not very strong, which aligns with previous research, which finds that digital infrastructure is more of an enabling than a determining factor of customer loyalty. (Aashish et al., 2025; Aber-Sawaeen & Aburumman, 2025) However, the significant, positive regression coefficient confirms previous empirical findings indicating that companies with stronger digital infrastructure are better positioned to improve customer experience and build long-term relationships. (Adil & Hendayana, 2025) Thus, the current observation supports the view that digital infrastructure competence is a sufficient, but not a determining, factor in enhancing customer loyalty and retention.

Unlike the weak impact on digital infrastructure capability, the results show a robust relationship between digital skills capability and sustainable, innovative performance. This finding is very consistent with the dynamic capabilities perspective, which emphasises the significance of firm-level skills and competencies in responding to technological and market change. (Alalwan et al., 2024; Borah et al., 2022) However, Budiarto and Nordin (2024) has already demonstrated that employees' digital capabilities enhance firms' capacity to adopt new technology, redesign processes, and develop innovative products and services.

Besides, the results support previous studies indicating that digital skills are more effective than simply having access to technology in driving innovation performance (Kahveci, 2025; Noer et al., 2025). Although digital resources are accessible to managers and employees through digital infrastructure, it is their digital capabilities that determine the success of these resources in facilitating continuous innovation and sustainability. Skilled staff also become a central factor in the SME environment, where resource limitations are often the norm, and digital transformation activities lead to long-term value creation rather than short-term operational benefits.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper has discovered that there is more subtle empirical evidence that digital capabilities do not consistently add to all dimensions of firm performance, suggesting that a differentiated conceptualisation of digital transformation in the SME context is necessary. Although this supports the idea that digital infrastructure is a relevant facilitator of customer retention, the lack of explanatory power suggests that infrastructure alone is not sufficient to achieve customer loyalty. It seems that the interaction of technological, relational, and strategic aspects is complex in its influence on customer loyalty and retention. This observation refutes overly deterministic premises in a subset of the digitalisation literature that assume adopting technology automatically leads to better customer performance, especially in resource-limited SME settings. The study concludes that although digital infrastructure provides the necessary foundation for enhanced sustainable

innovation performance. The results show that SMEs in Kwara State and other involved developing economies are more likely to benefit from strategic investments in digital skills development than from infrastructure expansion. Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered to SME owners and managers.

- i. The owners and managers of SMEs are advised to be more strategic in their digital transformation by moving beyond the acquisition of basic digital infrastructure to the systematic development of digital capabilities within their firms.
- ii. The government should ensure that they promote partnership among SMEs, higher learning institutions and technology transfer to assist in the transfer of knowledge and hands-on skills, as well as the creation of regional digital innovation hubs.

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